

THE VIRTUE OF THE NOBLE FAMILY OF THE PROPHET, MAY GOD BLESS HIM AND GRANT HIM PEACE, AND RATIONAL GUIDANCE

فضل آل بيت النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم الكرام وتوجيهات رشيدة

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Abstract

This research came to clarify and clarify the high morals of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, among his honorable family, his good behavior, his treatment, his kindness to his family, his high stature and the high status of his family. So that this would be in us a good example and a perfect example for all of his ummah, and it has five demands.

The Almighty said: (Indeed, you have in the Messenger of God a good example for those who hope in God and the Last Day and the Last Day)

And the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: "The most perfect of the believers in faith are those with the best manners, and the best of you are the best of your women in character. And the personal conditions of the Prophet - may God's prayers and peace be upon him- represent the applied approach to the directives of the Holy Qur'an, because the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, is the exalted role model in all the affairs of his life. It stems from solid divine foundations. It was the moral foundation that refined behavior, purified souls, negated customs, and kept what is consistent with the spirit of Islam, including it and forbade the other. As the conditions of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, were of such vitality and importance; this topic has been allocated according to the requirements of the study. This study was based on the extrapolation of the issues in which the opinions of scholars varied according to the multiplicity of factors related to the edge, according to an applied analytical methodology.

Keywords: Virtues, Ahl al-Bayt, the Prophet, the honorable.

ملخص البحث

جاء هذا البحث لتوضيح وبيان سمو أخلاق النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم بين أسرته الكريمة وخير تصرفه ومعاملته وعشرته لأهله وعلو منزلته ورفعة شأن أهله. حتى يكون ذلك فينا أسوة حسنة وقدوة مثالي لأمتنا جميعا. وفيه خمسة مطالب:

قال تعالى: (لَقَدْ كَانَ لَكُمْ فِي رَسُولِ اللَّهِ أُسْوَةٌ حَسَنَةٌ لِمَنْ كَانَ يَرْجُوا اللَّهَ وَالْيَوْمَ الْآخِرَ وَذَكَرَ اللَّهَ كَثِيرًا)

ويقول الرسول صلى الله عليه وسلم ((أكمل المؤمنين إيمانا أحسنهم خلقا وخياركم خياركم لنسائكم خلقا))

وأحوال النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم- الشخصية تمثل المنهج التطبيقي لتوجيهات القرآن الكريم لأن النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم هو القدوة العالية في جميع شئون حياته قال تعالى واصفا خلق نبيه : (وَإِنَّكَ لَعَلَى خُلُقٍ عَظِيمٍ) وحياء رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم الزوجية ينطلق من أسس ربانية متينة فكان الأساس الأخلاقي الذي هذب السلوك وطهر النفوس ونفى العادات وأبقى على ما يتوافق مع روح الإسلام منها ونهى عن الآخر.

ولما كان أحوال النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم بهذه الحيوية والأهمية؛ خصصت هذا الموضوع وفق ما اقتضته متطلبات الدراسة. ولقد قامت هذه الدراسة على استقراء المسائل التي تعددت آراء العلماء فيها تبعا لتعدد العوامل المتعلقة بالحافة وذلك وفق منهجية تطبيقية تحليلية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: فضائل, أهل, آل بيت, النبي, الكرام.

INTRODUCTION

Praise be to God, Lord of the Worlds, and prayers and peace be upon our master and Prophet Muhammad and all his family and companions. Then:

For every believer is a monotheist, imbuing himself, and his heart and mind looks forward to knowing the biography of the Master of the Messengers whom God has established as a guiding guide, and an imam to him calling, to chart his steps, to be guided by his guidance, and thereby obtain the approval of his Lord.

He also eagerly looks forward to knowing the biography of the Noble Prophet's House, and the pure offspring that the Prophet – may God's prayers and peace be upon him – raised, surrounded by the revelation of his Lord and watered it from the source of the purest prophecy, and the light of the supreme revelation, until it deserved the praise of God Almighty: Impurity, Ahl al-Bayt, and purifies you with a thorough purification (so that this pure and noble house would be an example and an example for him and his family. And reefs, and punishment and hills and panting and fees. The fragrant Prophetic biography and the history of the pure offspring are renewed at all times, guiding generations through its prolonged eras and its successive waves.

The first requirement: What is meant by the people of the house:

The scholars of Arabic and the imams of the religion have clarified the meaning of this compound word from the genitive and affixed with a clear explanation in which they made it clear that the first to enter this word was his wives, may God be pleased with them all, in contrast to the Rafidah who claim that what is meant by the people of the house are only four: Ali, Fatimah, Al-Hasan and Al-Hussain. Other than them and limiting them to Ahl al-Bayt in these four contradicts what the imams of the language have decided in what is meant by "the people of the house," rather it contradicts the Book and the Sunnah, and what the imams of the religion said. He is the most special of people to it, and the people of the house are its inhabitants, and the people of Islam are those who owe it."

Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani said in Al-Mufradat fi Gharib Al-Qur'an: "The people of a man are those who are united by lineage, religion, or whatever takes place in their industry, home and country. In the family of the Prophet, peace and blessings be upon him, absolutely, if it is said, "Ahl al-Bayt" because of his saying, the Mighty and Sublime, "God only desires to remove impurity from you, Ahl al-Bayt, and purify you."

And he crossed the man's family about his wife, and the people of Islam with whom he unites... until he said: "And a man is qualified if he marries." And from it it was said: "God destroyed you in Paradise, meaning: He married you in it and made for you in it people who unite you and them."

And it came in Lisan Al-Arab to Ibn Manzur: "And the people of the sect: who owes it, the people of Islam who owe it, the people of the command and its rulers, the people of the house its residents, and the people of the man: the most specific of people with it, and the people of the Prophet's house, peace be upon him, his wives, daughters and son-in-law, I mean Ali, peace be upon him." And it was said: "The women of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace.. until he said: Qualification: marriage, and the family who has a wife and children, and the bachelor who has no wife.. and the family of a man is his family, and the family of God and His Messenger are his guardians."

And it came in the bride's crown: "And the family of the sect is he who adheres to it and believes in it, and the family is for the man his wife and his children enter into it." And with it he explained the Almighty's saying: "And he walked with his family" meaning: "His wife and his family and the family of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, his wives, daughters and son-in-law Ali, may God be pleased with him or his wives, and it was said: His family الرجال الذين هم آله ويدخل فيه الأحفاد والذريات"، ومنه قوله تعالى: {وَأْمُرْ أَهْلَكَ بِالصَّلَاةِ وَاصْطَبِرْ عَلَيْهَا لَا نَسْأَلُكَ رِزْقًا نَحْنُ نَرْزُقُكَ وَالْعَاقِبَةُ لِلتَّقْوَى} وقوله تعالى: {إِنَّمَا يُرِيدُ اللَّهُ لِيُذْهِبَ عَنْكُمُ الرِّجْسَ أَهْلَ الْبَيْتِ وَيُطَهِّرَكُمْ تَطْهِيرًا} And the Almighty's saying: {They said, "Do you marvel at the command of God, and the mercy and blessings of God be upon you, Ahl al-Bayt"? Indeed, He is praiseworthy.

And the people of every prophet are his nation and the people of his creed, and from him is the verse: وقد وردت لفظة "أهل البيت" في سياق الخطاب لأزواج النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم قال تعالى: {وَقَرْنَ فِي بُيُوتِكُنَّ وَلَا تَبَرَّجْنَ تَبَرُّجَ الْجَاهِلِيَّةِ الْأُولَى وَأَقِمْنَ الصَّلَاةَ وَآتِينَ الزَّكَاةَ وَأَطِعْنَ اللَّهَ وَرَسُولَهُ إِنَّمَا يُرِيدُ اللَّهُ لِيُذْهِبَ عَنْكُمُ الرِّجْسَ أَهْلَ الْبَيْتِ وَيُطَهِّرَكُمْ تَطْهِيرًا (33) وَادْكُرْنَ مَا} The verses of God and the wisdom are recited in your homes, for God is kind and acquainted with it.

Whoever has the slightest knowledge of the Book of God Almighty will understand from these two verses that what is meant by "his family" are his wives, may the peace and blessings of God be upon him, because the beginning of the verse "and a bond" and the verses before and after it were addressed only to the mothers of the believers, may God be pleased with them and their satisfaction.

Al-Qurtubi, may God Almighty have mercy on him, said in al-Jami` al-Ahkam al-Qur'an: "What appears from the verse is that it is general in all members of the household, whether spouses or others. The wives are members of the household, because the verse is about them and the address to them is indicated by the context of the speech. The scholar Ibn al-Qayyim said in Jala' al-Afham in prayer and peace be upon the best of people, after citing the verses in which the address was addressed to the wives of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him in Surat Al-

Ahzab, he said: "So they entered the family of the house because this speech is all in the context of mentioning them, so it is not permissible to take them out from something of it, and God knows best."

Al-Hafiz Ibn Katheer, may God Almighty have mercy on him, said in the interpretation of the great Qur'an: And the Almighty's saying: "God only desires to remove impurity from you, O people of the household, and to purify you." One, either alone according to one saying or with others according to the correct one... until he said: Then who does not In it, whoever manages the Qur'an is that the women of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, are inside the Almighty saying: And the wisdom is that God was kind, an expert (that is: "Know what God, the Blessed and Most High, sends down to His Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, in your homes of the Book and the Sunnah. And Aisha Al-Siddiqah, the daughter of Al-Siddiq, may God be pleased with them both, bestowed this blessing on them and gave them this booty, and singled them out from this great mercy, for the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, did not receive revelation in the bed of a woman other than her, as stated by the blessings and peace of God be upon him. Some scholars, may God have mercy on them, said: Because He did not marry a virgin other than her, and no man slept with her in her bed except the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, and may God be pleased with her. with this designation. As it was presented in the hadith, "The people of my house are more deserving."

And he, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, made clear what is meant by "people of the house" and that what is meant first by that are his wives, peace and blessings be upon him. Al-Bukhari narrated with his chain of transmission to Anas bin Malik in the story of his marriage, peace and blessings be upon him, to Zainab bint Jahsh, in which he went out and went to Aisha's room and said: "Peace be upon you, people." The house and the mercy of God." She said: "And upon you be peace and the mercy of God. How did you find your family, may God bless you?" So he read the stone of his wives, all of them, he says to them, as he says to Aisha, and they tell him as Aisha said. There is no dispute about that except for the one whose heart has been imprinted on slander against the companions of the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, who are the elite of this nation, may God be pleased with them and their lands.

The scholar Ibn al-Qayyim mentioned in Jalal al-Afham in Prayers and Peace be upon the best of people, that the imams differed in defining what is meant by "the family of the house" according to sayings: He said, may God have mercy on him: They have to give charity, and among them are three sayings of the scholars:

One of them is that they are Banu Hashim, and Banu al-Muttalib, and this is the doctrine of Imam al-Shafi'i and Imam Ahmad in a narration from him.

The second: They are Banu Hashim in particular. This is the doctrine of Imam Abu Hanifa, may God have mercy on him, and a narration on the authority of Imam Ahmad, may God have mercy on him, and the choice of Ibn al-Qasim, the owner of Imam Malik.

The third: They are Banu Hashim, and from above them to Ghalib, so Banu al-Muttalib, Banu Umayyah, Banu Nawfal and from above them to Banu Ghalib, and it is the choice of Ashhab among the companions of Imam Malik, may God have mercy on him.. Until he said: And this saying about the family, I mean, that they are the ones for whom charity is forbidden is one of the texts Imam al-Shafi'i, may God have mercy on him, and Imam Ahmad, may God have mercy on him, and many others, and it is the choice of the majority of the companions of Imam Ahmad and Imam al-Shafi'i. The second saying: That the family of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, are his offspring and his wives, especially Ibn Abd al-Barr in the preface.

The third saying: That his family, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, are his followers until the Day of Resurrection. It was narrated by Ibn Abd al-Bar on the authority of some of the people of knowledge. The oldest of this saying was narrated by Jaber bin Abdullah.

The fourth saying: That his family, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, are the pious of his nation. Judge Hussein narrated it.

As told by the willing and a group. And when he, may God have mercy on him, finished presenting the evidence for each saying and clarifying what is in it from the correct and weak, he said likely: "The correct one is the first saying, followed by the second. As for the third and fourth, they are weak because the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, raised the suspicion by saying: "Charity is not appropriate for the family of Muhammad." And his saying: "Only the family of Muhammad eats from this money," and his saying: "Oh God, make the sustenance of the family of Muhammad food," and this cannot be meant by the generality of the nation definitely.

The second requirement: the general virtues of the family of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace:

Praise was received in the Book and the Sunnah on the Companions of the family of the Prophet, peace and blessings be upon him, male and female in general, in other than any verse and hadith, and as we presented in the preface before this

that his wives are included in the family of his household as a primary entry, and Qur'anic verses have been mentioned in praising them in general. God Almighty made it clear in them that they are in a high rank and a high rank.

قال تعالى: (الَّذِي أَوْلَىٰ بِالْمُؤْمِنِينَ مِنْ أَنفُسِهِمْ وَأَزْوَاجُهُ أُمَّهَاتُهُمْ وَأُولُوا الْأَرْحَامِ بَعْضُهُمْ أَوْلَىٰ بِبَعْضٍ فِي كِتَابِ اللَّهِ مِنَ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ وَالْمُهَاجِرِينَ إِلَّا أَنْ تَفْعَلُوا إِلَيَّ ۗ) 1- This noble verse included a great and noble virtue for all his wives, may the prayers and peace of God be upon him, which is that the Almighty: enjoined for them the rule of motherhood over every believer, with the honor they have of the companionship of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him.

Al-Qurtubi, may God have mercy on him, said in Al-Jami` al-Ahkam al-Qur'an: "God honored the wives of His Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, by making them the mothers of the believers, i.e., in the obligation of veneration, righteousness, reverence, and the prohibition of marriage on men, and he withheld them, may God be pleased with them, in contrast to mothers."

Al-Hafiz Ibn Kathir, may God Almighty have mercy on him, said in the interpretation of the great Qur'an: "And the Almighty's saying: "And his wives are their mothers" meaning: "In sanctity, respect, reverence, honor and honor, but it is not permissible to be alone with them and the prohibition does not spread to their daughters and sisters unanimously." ومن مناقبه العظيمة التي سجلها له القرآن العظيم أنهم اخترن الله ورسوله والدار الآخرة إيثاراً منهن لذلك على الدنيا وزينتها فأعد الله لهن على ذلك 2- Beautiful (28) ثواباً جزيلاً وأجرًا عظيمًا قال تعالى: (يَا أَيُّهَا النَّبِيُّ قُلْ لِأَزْوَاجِكَ إِنْ كُنْتُمْ تُرِيدُونَ الْحَيَاةَ الدُّنْيَا وَزِينَتَهَا فَتَعَالَيْنَ أُمْعَمَكُنَّ وَأَسْرَحَكُنَّ سَرَاحًا) And if you desire God and His Messenger, and the abode of Then God has prepared a great reward for good deeds among you (29). In this is a statement of a great virtue and a high rank for his wives, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, who are the first to be given the word "Ahl al-Bayt".

3- Among their public morals, may God be pleased with them all, is that God Almighty has told His servants that their reward for obedience and righteous deeds is equal to the reward of others. The Almighty said: {And whoever among you is obedient to God and His Messenger and works righteousness, its reward shall be doubled.

4- Among their common virtues that the Lord of the worlds honored them with and told His servants in His Mighty Book is that they are not like any of the women in virtue, honor and lofty status. The Almighty said: "O women of the Prophet, you are not like any other of the women.

5- Among the general virtues of his wives, peace and blessings be upon him, that God mentioned in his dear book is what he blessed them with by reciting his verses, and what was revealed from the revelation, peace be upon him, in their homes. This is a great veil and a great pride for them, may God be pleased with them all. in your homes from the signs of God and of wisdom, for God is kind and well-acquainted. In this noble verse, there is a speech to the mothers of the believers that they remember God's blessing upon them by placing them in homes in which God's verses and wisdom are recited.

Ibn Jarir al-Tabari, may God Almighty have mercy on him, said in Jami' al-Bayan: "And what he meant by his saying:)And mention the verses of God that are recited in your homes. God was not revealed to him by the Qur'an and that Sunnah." And his saying: "God was kind and an expert." God Almighty says: "God was kind to you when He made you in the houses in which His verses and wisdom are recited, expert in you when He chose you for His Messenger, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, spouses. "

6- Among the general venerations that God honored the Companions from the family of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, told him that the Almighty told him that he purified them from the abomination in purification, and he noted this in the text of his noble book. and His Messenger, God only desires to remove impurity from you, O people of the household, and to purify you with a thorough purification.

This verse is inclusive of all the members of his household, peace and blessings of God be upon him, from the Companions, male and female, and not one of them departs from it, and all of them, God removed impurity from them and purified them from it with a thorough purification.

It was said: Sin. It was said: Shirk. He said: Satan.

And it was said: evil actions and reprehensible morals, so evil deeds: such as indecency, whether apparent or hidden, and reprehensible morals: such as stinginess, miserliness, envy and severing the ties of kinship.

Al-Baghawi, may God Almighty have mercy on him, said in Tafsir al-Baghawi: "He meant by uncleanness: the sin that God forbade women from." Muqatil said: Ibn Abbas said: "It means the work of Satan and that in which God has no pleasure." And Qatada said: "It means bad." Mujahid said: "The abomination of doubt, and he meant the people of the house, the wives of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, because they are in his house, which is the narration of Saeed bin Jubayr on the authority of Ibn Abbas."

Removing uncleanness includes his wives, peace and blessings be upon him, and other companions of his household, may God be pleased with them all, for God has removed impurity from them and purified them thoroughly. The verse is comprehensive for the wives, Ali, Fatimah, Al-Hasan and Al-Hussain, may God be pleased with them all.

As for the wives, all of them are referred to in the context of the verse, and because they are the dwellers in his houses, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, who are staying in his homes.

As for the entry of Ali, Fatima, Al-Hasan and Al-Hussein, because they are his relatives and the people of his family in lineage, and this is supported by the hadiths that declare that they are from his family, and among those hadiths what Muslim narrated with his chain of transmission to the mother of the believers Aisha, may God be pleased with her, she said: With black hair, Al-Hasan Ibn Ali came and entered it, then Al-Hussain came and he entered with him, then Fatimah came and he entered it, then Ali came and he entered it, then he said: "God only wants to remove the abomination from you, Ahl al-Bayt.

Imam al-Qurtubi said in al-Jami' Ahkam al-Qur'an: This is an invitation from the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, to them after the revelation of the verse. It has also been proven with the correct transmission that these verses, when they were revealed, were read by the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, to his wives. There have been many hadiths showing the superiority of Ahl al-Bayt in general, including:

Al-Hakim narrated with his chain of transmission to Abu Saeed Al-Khudri, may God be pleased with him, who said: The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: "By the One in Whose Hand is my soul, none of the Ahl al-Bayt hates us except that God will enter him into the Fire." And Muslim narrated with his chain of transmission to Yazid bin Hayyan, he said: "Husayn bin Sabrah and Umar bin Muslim and I went to Zaid bin Arqam. I met you, Zaid, very well. Zaid told us what you heard from the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, he said: "Oh my nephew, by God, I have grown old, my covenant has advanced, and I have forgotten some of what I was aware of from the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace. Then he said: One day the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, gave us a sermon at a water called Khuma between Makkah and Madinah, so he praised God, praised him, exhorted and mentioned, then said: "But after that, O people, I am only human, and the Messenger of my Lord is about to come. The first of them is the Book of God, in which is guidance and light, so take the Book of God and hold fast to it." He urged God's book and desired it, then said: "And the people of my house, I remind you of God in my family, I remind you of God in my family, I remind you of God in my family." My house." So Husayn said to him: "Who are the people of his house, Zaid? Aren't his women from the people of his house?" He said: "His women are from the people of his house, but the people of his house are those who were forbidden to give charity after him." He said: "And who are they?" He said: They are the family of Ali, the family of Aqeel, the family of Jaafar and the family of Abbas. He said: All of these have forbidden charity. He said: Yes.

Al-Hakim narrated with his chain of transmission to Abdullah bin Abbas, may God be pleased with them both, that the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: "Oh, sons of Abd al-Muttalib, I have asked God for you three things: to make your stand firm, to guide your lost, and to teach your ignorant, and I asked God to make you good, noble, merciful. Between the corner and the shrine, he prayed and fasted, then met God while he hated the people of Muhammad's house and entered the Fire." This hadith included three virtues for the family of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, and they are clear as the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, explained.

The third requirement: God commanded the wives of the Prophet to decide in the homes:

The decision in the house does not mean staying at home and never leaving it, but it is a nice gesture until the house is the residence and the origin in their lives, and it is the headquarters for them, because it is the factory from which the heroic men come out. But do not do as the negligent ones do, loitering in the streets, adorning themselves in their appearance to show their adornment, until they attract attention to them, and seduce young people by seducing them, but rather come out with decency and dignity, as the Almighty said:

"And do not display your adornment like that of the pre-Islamic era": that is, do not display your adornment and your beauties, as the women of the pre-Islamic era used to do, when women would go out to the market, displaying their virtues, revealing what is not appropriate to reveal from her body.

Muqatil said: "The woman would throw the veil over her head and not pull it, so her necklaces, earrings and neck would appear." Qatada said: "They had a gait in which they broke and sang, so God forbade that." Ibn Kathir said in the sayings of the scholars of the Salaf: "A woman among them would pass between men, uncovering her chest, and perhaps showing her neck and the ends of her hair." The readers differed in the reading of the word "Qarn" in two ways: The first side: Fath Al-Qaf, and Nafi', Abu Jaafar Al-Madani, and Asim recited it. And that is according to the language of the people of Hijaz: I decided - by breaking the r - I decided - to open the Qaf - in the place: if I stayed there.

The second side: by breaking the qaf, and the rest of the ten reciters recited in this way. Whoever reverences acknowledges reverence, i.e.: dwells, and the command from it: reverence - by breaking the qaf - and for women: qarn.

And it may be from the decision, not the reverence, she says: I decided in the place, I agree, and the original: I decided, I omitted the one ra to reduce, and they transferred its movement to the qaf, and dispensed with the thousand wasl by moving the qaf. The cooler said.

On both readings, the meaning of the verse is clear in God Almighty's command to the women of His Prophet to stay in the homes and accompany them, and not to leave it except for an excuse, as the frequent departure from her home is one of the reprehensible qualities that are not befitting a righteous woman, so how are the women of the Prophet, peace and blessings of God be upon him. The Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, instructed the women of his nation to stay in the homes and not leave them except for a need. Indeed, when he, peace and blessings be upon him, forbade preventing women from going to mosques, he emphasized that "their homes are better for them."

The commentators differed a lot about what is meant by the first ignorance, and what appears and the knowledge of God is that describing the Jahiliyyah is the first revealing description, because it is first before Islam, and Islam came after it, so there are no two Jahiliyyah, first and second.

a - The difference between the hijab, the jilbab and the khimaar.

Hijab linguistically: the veiling veils the veil, the veiling of the thing veils it, the veil, the veil that veils it, its veil, and a veiled woman has veiled with veil.

Hijab idiomatically: It is covering the entire body of a woman except the face and hands.

b - the jilbab language: the jilbab is a shirt and the jilbab is a garment wider than the khimaar without the robe with which the woman covers her head and chest.

The jilbab idiomatically: Ibn Taymiyyah defined it in Majmoo' al-Fatwas: "The cover, it is also called: the robe, and the common name is the izar, which is what covers her head and the rest of her body."

c - The khimaar language: the half, and it was said that a woman covers her head and combines it with khmer and khmer.

idiomatically: it is what a woman covers her head and face with, with which she hides from the eyes of men.

The fourth requirement: God commanded them to wear the veil:

The command to veil is mentioned in two places in this noble surah:

الأول: أمر الله سبحانه وتعالى المسلمين إذا أرادوا سؤال زوجات النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم شيئاً أن يكون من حجاب، فقال تعالى: ﴿يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَدْخُلُوا بُيُوتَ النَّبِيِّ إِلَّا أَنْ يُؤَدَّ لَكُمْ إِلَى طَعَامٍ غَيْرَ نَاظِرِينَ إِنَاهُ وَلَكِنْ إِذَا دُعِيتُمْ فَادْخُلُوا فَإِذَا طَعِمْتُمْ فَانْتَسِرُوا وَلَا مَسْتَأْذِنِينَ لِحَدِيثٍ إِنَّ ذَلِكَ كَانَ يُؤْذِي النَّبِيَّ فَيَسْتَجِيبُ مِنْكُمْ وَاللَّهُ لَا يَسْتَجِيبُ مِنَ الْحَقِّ وَإِذَا سَأَلْتُمُوهُنَّ مَتَاعًا فَاسْأَلُوهُنَّ مِنْ وَرَاءِ حِجَابٍ ذَلِكُمْ أَطْهَرُ لِقُلُوبِكُمْ وَقُلُوبِهِنَّ وَمَا كَانَ لَكُمْ أَنْ تُؤَدُّوا رَسُولَ اللَّهِ وَلَا أَنْ تُنْكِحُوا زُرَّاجَهُ مِنْ بَعْدِهِ أَبَدًا إِنَّ ذَلِكَ كَانَ عِنْدَ اللَّهِ عَظِيمًا﴾.

الثاني: ثم جاء الأمر من الله سبحانه وتعالى لنساء النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم بالحجاب صراحة، وذلك في قوله تعالى: ﴿يَا أَيُّهَا النَّبِيُّ قُلْ لَأزْوَاجِكُمْ وَبَنَاتِكُمْ وَنِسَاءَ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ يُدْنِينَ عَلَيْهِنَّ مِنْ جَلَابِيبِهِنَّ ذَلِكَ أَدْنَى أَنْ يُعْرَفْنَ فَلَا يُؤْذَيْنَ وَكَانَ اللَّهُ غَفُورًا رَحِيمًا﴾. Through these two verses, it is known that the veil was imposed by God Almighty on the wives of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, in particular, and Muslim women in general.

The noble verses have clarified the purpose of imposing the veil in two matters:

The first: Purity in hearts, "That is purer for your hearts and theirs."

Two: respect Respecting the veiled woman and not harming her, "That is the shortest for them to be known and not to be offended."

The fifth requirement: the prohibition of submissiveness in words and speaking with kindness:

The Almighty says: "Do not be submissive by word, lest he who has a disease in his heart may be tempted, and speak a kind word."

A letter addressed by God Almighty to the wives of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, and after them to all the Muslim women: that their words in the presence of men (other than the mahrams and the husband) should not be tender, soft, and arrogant, showing the woman's femininity in which men's hearts and desires tend to her; Rather, their speech is a harsh chapter without raising the voice, or speaking much, but her words are as much as the need, like a short answer to a question, because the words are similar to their words the words of suspicious women and prostitutes. God Almighty has forbidden them, when addressing men, to have that softness in their tone, which stirs up the desires of men, stirs their instincts and forbids them. That in a woman's voice, when she utters and softens in her speech, is what stirs greed in the hearts of men, and stirs up sedition in sick souls, and if the Qur'an forbids a woman to be unyielding in her speech with foreign men, lest the immoral and ungodly covet covetousness, so how about those who provoke the latent and melancholy, with fluid singing The insolent, who is all fluid and dissolute, and an invitation to what stirs sedition, provokes lust, and awakens the sexual instinct? I mean, there is nothing wrong with talking to a foreigner at the time of necessity, but the woman's tone and the way she speaks in these situations must be in such a way that the heart of the person she is speaking does not fall into the slightest imagining of the possibility of something else from her. Her words are joking and flirting, or there is any intentional tenderness or sweetness in her voice that stirs

the feelings of the listener and provokes his emotions, thus encouraging him, so he covets and dares. Submission in words is humility and humility, it is said: submissive, submissive, submissive, and submissive: a man is submissive, and a woman is submissive: what is meant in the verse: softness and gentleness in speech, inherent in compliant leadership. Submission may be verbal in the same words, their marble and their appearance, even if the meaning is not suspicious, and the Arabs use the word submission in the sense of inclination and spinning as well, and from it is the saying of Laila Al-Akhiliya, where Al-Hajjaj said: Have you ever seen anything from Al-Khafaji's repentance that you hate? I said: No, by God, Prince, but he recited to me a poem one day, and I thought that he had submitted to some order, so I sang to him:

And who has a need, we said to him: Do not disclose it, for there is no way for it as long as I live

The Almighty said: "If you are pious." The scholars differed as to what is related to this sentence: some of them said: It relates to what came before it, and the meaning: "O women of the Prophet, you are not like one of the women. Some of them said: Taqwa is related to what follows it, so the meaning is: "If you fear Allah, do not be submissive." Shawkani preferred the first. Then the Almighty explained the reason for which He commanded them to do this, which is: "Submitting in sayings causes a great evil." And the disease is its reality: the disorder of the mood of the body due to the weakness of strength, and here it is borrowed from the imbalance of religious scruples. It may mean: "immorality and immorality," as Ikrimah said. Both are contained in the meaning of the verse. Then the Almighty said: {And say a kind word.} After God Almighty forbade them from being humble in speech, He commanded them to speak kindly, and this command came after the prohibition in order to avoid any illusion that God Almighty commanded them to lower their voices as a secret hadith. And what is known: It is the right thing that the Sharia does not hate, and the words that people are familiar with according to general custom, and the people of immorality and immorality do not covet them to slander them.

The results of the research:

The virtue of the wives of the Prophet by distinguishing them from others if they adhere to the law of God.

A statement that what is meant by Ahl al-Bayt includes all the mothers of the believers.

The verses talked about the purification of the family of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace.

- It has become clear with conclusive evidence that the statement of the Shiites is false that what is meant by the family of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, are Fatima, Ali, al-Hasan and al-Husayn, rather what is meant here are the wives of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace.
- God Almighty forbade the wives of the Prophet - may God's prayers and peace be upon him - to be gentle in speech, to be submissive to it, and to show off, and commanded them to stay in homes, and to persevere in obedience to God and to the Messenger - may God's prayers and peace be upon him, and to teach the Qur'an and Sunnah, and remind us of knowledge.
- God Almighty gave the wives of the Prophet - may God's prayers and peace be upon him - between this world and the hereafter, so choose God and His Messenger, and prefer a life of subsistence and austerity in living in this world with a desire for bliss in the Hereafter.

And God Almighty made it clear that they are not like other women in terms of reward and punishment, so if they are pious, their reward will be doubled in this world and the hereafter. The disobedience was punished by weakness.

May God's peace and blessings be upon our Prophet Muhammad and his family and companions, and our last prayer is praise be to God, Lord of the Worlds.

Margins:

Surah Al-Ahzab Verse 21

2- It was included by Imam Abu Dawood in his Sunan (2/pg. 632/Kitab al-Sunnah/Chapter of Evidence for the increase of hadith 4682) he said: Ahmad ibn Hanbal told us Yahya ibn Sa'id on the authority of faith and its decrease by Muhammad ibn Amr on the authority of Abu Salamah on the authority of Abu Hurairah.

- Surah Al-Qalam verse (5)

- Surah Al-Ahzab verse 33

3- Tafsir al-Qummi (2/193), and al-Safi fi tafsir al-Qur'an (2/351-352), al-Fayd al-Kashani: Muhammad Mohsen ibn Murtada ibn Mahmoud, al-Fayd al-Kashani. (D 1007 AH), (T 1091 AH).

1- Language standards, (1/150) by Abu Al-Hasan Al-Razi.

2- Imam Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani, Al-Hasan bin Muhammad bin Al-Mufaddal, Abu Al-Qasim, (T. 502 AH) see: Takhreej Al-Hana'at (2/1177) Al-Nakhshabi.

3- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (33).

4- Vocabulary in the stranger of the Qur'an, (p.: 29) by Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani.

5- Lisan Al Arab, (11/29-30) Ibn Al-Mansur.

6- Surat Al-Qasas, verse: (29).

1- Surah Taha, verse: (132).

2- Surah Al-Ahzab verse: (33).

3- Surat Hud, verse: (73).

- 4- The Bride's Crown, (7/217) Al-Zubaidi.
- 5- Surat Maryam, verse: (55).
- 6- Surah Al-Ahza b, verse: (33-34).
- 7- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (33-34). Al-Jami` al-Ahkam al-Qur'an (14/183) Al-Qurtubi.
- 1- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (30-34).
- 2- Jala' al-Afham in Prayers and Peace be upon the Best of People, (p.: 117), Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya.
- 3- Interpretation of the Great Qur'an, (5/452, 458), Ibn Katheer. And his saying: "As presented in the hadith, "And the people of my house are more deserving" refers to a hadith narrated by Imam Ahmad in Al-Musnad (4/107), and Al-Bukhari in his Sahih, Chapter on the Merits of the Relationship of the Messenger (No.: 6452).
 - Sahih Al-Bukhari, (4/1800, No.: 4515).
- 1- Imam Ashhab bin Abdul Aziz Al-Qaisi, Abu Amr Ashhab bin Abdul Aziz bin Daoud bin Ibrahim Al-Jaadi, the Egyptian Maliki jurist (d. 204 AH) see: Takhreej Al-Hana'at, (2/1177) Al-Nakhshabi.
- 2- Imam Al-Shafi'i, Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Idris Al-Shafi'i Al-Muttalib Al-Qurashi, (d. 150 AH), (d. 204 AH) see: Majma' Al-Zawa'id (6/100) Al-Haythami.
- 3- Imam Ahmad bin Hanbal, Abu Abdullah Ahmed bin Muhammad bin Hanbal bin Hilal Al-Dhahili Al-Shaibani Al-Marwazi Al-Baghdadi, (d. 164 AH), (d. 241 AH). See: Majma' al-Zawa'id (6/100) Al-Haythami.
- 4- Imam Jaber bin Abdullah: He is Jaber bin Abdullah bin Amr bin Haram bin Kaab bin Ghannam bin Kaab bin Salamah. His mother was Nusaiba bint Uqbah bin Adi from Banu Salamah. See: Majma' al-Zawa'id (6/100) al-Haythami.
- 5- Imam Al-Qadi Hussain bin Muhammad bin Ahmed Al-Allamah, Sheikh of the Shafi'is in Khorasan Abu Ali Al-Marwadhi, (d. 462 AH).
- 1- Imam Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani: He is Abu Al-Qasim Al-Hussein bin Muhammad, known as Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani. (died: 502 AH) See: Tahrej Al-Hainat (2/1177) Al-Nakhshabi.
- 2- Al-Bukhari included it in his Sahih, Book of the Merits of the Messenger of God, Chapter: Leaving the Use of Ahl al-Bayt on Charity (No. 6460), and in Sahih Muslim, Book of the Merits of the Messenger of God, Chapter: The Virtue and Status of Ahl al-Bayt, (2/111, Number: 1055).
- 3- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (6).
- 4- Al-Ahkam Al-Qur'an, (14/123) Al-Qurtubi.
- 1- Interpretation of the Great Qur'an (5/425), Ibn Kathir.
- 2- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (28/29).
- 3- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (31).
- 4- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (32).
- 5- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (34).
- 1- Imam Ibn Jarir al-Tabari: He is Muhammad ibn Jarir ibn Yazid ibn Kathir ibn Ghalib, (d. 310 AH), (d. 224 AH). See: Majma' al-Zawa'id (6/100) al-Haythami.
- 2- Jami' al-Bayan, (22/9) al-Tabari.
- 3- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (33).
- 4- The provisions of the Qur'an, (3/571) by Ibn al-Arabi. Al-Masir (6/381) added by Ibn al-Jawzi.
- 5- Qatada bin Al-Nu'man: Qatada bin Al-Nu'man bin Zaid Al-Ansari Al-Awsi, then Al-Dhafri is called Abu Amr, and it was said: Abu Omar, and it was said: Abu Abdullah. (T 23 AH) See: Majma' Al-Zawa'id (6/100) Al-Haythami.
- 1- The features of the download on the interpretation of Al-Khazen (5/212) Al-Baghawi.
- 2- Al-Murat: a garment that is made of wool, and it may be of prick or something else. See: The End in Gharib Hadith (4/319), by Ibn Al-Atheer.
- 3- Sahih Muslim, chapter on the interpretation of Surat Al-Ahzab (4/1883, No.: 2424).
- 4- Al-Jami' of the provisions of the Qur'an, (14/184) Al-Qurtubi.
- 5- See: Tuhfat al-Ahwadhi with the explanation of Sahih al-Tirmidhi, (9/67) Abd al-Rahman al-Mubarakfuri.
- 1 - See: Sahih Muslim, No.: 2408. It was included by Al-Naysaburi in Al-Mustadrak in the Book of Knowledge of the Companions, Chapter on the Merits of the People of the House of the Messenger of God, peace and blessings be upon him, (3/150), and Al-Dhahabi was silent about it in his summary and cited in the biography of the nobles' flags (2/123).
- 2- Saffron: He stood or stood with his legs apart. See: The End in Gharib Hadith (3/39) Ibn Al-Atheer.
- 3- Narrated by Al-Naysaburi Al-Mustadrak in the Book of Knowledge of the Companions, Chapter on the Merits of the House of the Messenger (784/4).
- 1- See: Tafsir Ibn Kathir (3/491).
- 2- Al-Badour Al-Zahira in the Ten Frequent Readings, (p.: 254), Abdel-Fattah Al-Qadi (d. 1325 AH), (d. 1403 AH).
- 3- Nafi' bin Al-Azraq, famous for questioning Ibn Abbas. See: Majma' al-Zawa'id (p. 6/306) al-Haythami.
- 4- Abu Jaafar Yazid bin al-Qaqa' al-Makhzumi al-Madani, my follower and one of the ten reciters. (died 130 AH). See: Majma' al-Zawa'id (9/142) al-Haythami.
- 5- Abu Bakr Asim bin Bahdala bin Abi Al-Nujud Al-Asadi Al-Kufi, one of the followers who read in Kufa after Abu Abd Al-Rahman Al-Salami, died in 128 AH. See: Majma' al-Zawa'id, (9/142) Al-Haythami.
- 1- See: Tafsir Al-Shawkani, (4/269), and Ibn Attia's interpretation (p. 1511).
- 2- Abu Dawood included it in his Sunan from the hadith of Abdullah bin Omar, may God be pleased with them, with the wording: "Do not prevent your women from mosques, and their homes are better for them." The Book of Prayer, chapter on what came about women going out to mosques, No.: 567, (1/155).

- 3- This is what is most likely, and Imam Ibn Attia went to him in his interpretation (p. 1412), and Imam Ibn Ashour in Tahrir and Enlightenment, (22/13).
- 4- Lisan Al-Arab (1/352), Ibn Al-Mansur.
- 5- The veil of women between religions and secularism, (p. 13), Huda Darwish.
- 1- Lisan al-Arab (1/323) by Ibn al-Mansur.
- 2- Majmoo' al-Fatawa, (22/110), Ibn Taymiyyah.
- 3- Lisan Al Arab (4/299), Ibn Al-Mansur.
- 4- Surat Al-Ahzab, Verse: (53).
- 5- Surat Al-Ahzab, Verse: (59).
- 1- Surat Al-Ahzab, verse: (32).
- 2- See: Tawfiq al-Rahman in the lessons of the Qur'an, (3/498), Faisal bin Abdul Aziz Al Mubarak.
- 3- See: Tafsir Ibn Ashour (22/9).
- 1- Songs, 3/245. By Abu Al-Faraj Al-Isfahani, and Diwan Al-Sabbabah (p.: 90) by Ibn Abi Hijla.
- 2- See: Keys to the Unseen, 25/180 Al-Razi.
- 3- See: Fath Al-Qadeer (4/269), Al-Shawkani.
- 4- Interpretation of Ibn Ashour, (22/9).
- 5- The interpretation of Ibn Attia, (p. 1511), the interpretation of Al-Shawkani (4/269), and the interpretation of Abi Al-Saud (7/102).
- 6- Interpretation of Ibn Ashour, (22/9).
- 7- See: Tafsir Ibn Atiyah (p. 1511), Tafsir Ibn Ashour (22/9), and Tafsir Al-Shawkani (4/269).

Resources and References

- [1]. Tafsir al-Qummi (2/193), and al-Safi fi tafsir al-Qur'an (2/351-352), al-Fayd al-Kashani: Muhammad Mohsen ibn Murtada ibn Mahmoud, al-Fayd al-Kashani. (D 1007 AH), (T 1091 AH).
- [2]. Language standards, (1/150) by Abu Al-Hasan Al-Razi.
- [3]. Imam Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani, Al-Hasan bin Muhammad bin Al-Mufaddal, Abu Al-Qasim, (T. 502 AH) see: Takhreej Al-Hana'at (2/1177) Al-Nakhshabi.
- [4]. Vocabulary in the stranger of the Qur'an, (p.: 29) by Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani.
- [5]. The Bride's Crown, (7/217) Al-Zubaidi.
- [6]. Jala' al-Afham in Prayers and Peace be upon the Best of People, (p.: 117), Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya.
- [7]. Interpretation of the Great Qur'an, (5/452, 458), Ibn Katheer. And he said: "As it was presented in the Death "and my family is more deserving" refers to
- [8]. Sahih Al-Bukhari, (4/1800, No.: 4515).
- [9]. Imam Ashhab bin Abdul Aziz Al-Qaisi, Abu Amr Ashhab bin Abdul Aziz bin Daoud bin Ibrahim Al-Jaadi, the Egyptian Maliki jurist (d. 204 AH) see: Takhreej Al-Hana'at, (2/1177) Al-Nakhshabi.
- [10]. Al-Ahkam Al-Qur'an, (14/123) Al-Qurtubi.
- [11]. Interpretation of the Great Qur'an (5/425), Ibn Kathir.
- [12]. Jami' al-Bayan, (22/9) al-Tabari.
- [13]. The provisions of the Qur'an, (3/571) by Ibn al-Arabi. Al-Masir (6/381) added by Ibn al-Jawzi.
- [14]. Majma' al-Zawa'id, (6/100) al-Haythami.
- [15]. The features of the download on the interpretation of Al-Khazen (5/212) Al-Baghawi.
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- [17]. Al-Jami' of the provisions of the Qur'an, (14/184) Al-Qurtubi.
- [18]. See: Tuhfat al-Ahwadhi with the explanation of Sahih al-Tirmidhi, (9/67) Abd al-Rahman al-Mubarakfuri.
- [19]. Al-Badour Al-Zahira in the Ten Frequent Readings, (p.: 254), Abdel-Fattah Al-Qadi (d. 1325 AH), (d. 1403 AH).
- [20]. See: Tafsir Al-Shawkani, (4/269), and Ibn Attia's interpretation (p. 1511).
- [21]. Lisan Al-Arab (1/352), Ibn Al-Mansur.
- [22]. The veil of women between religions and secularism, (p. 13), Huda Darwish.
- [23]. Lisan al-Arab (1/323) by Ibn al-Mansur.
- [24]. Majmoo' al-Fatawa, (22/110), Ibn Taymiyyah.
- [25]. See: Tawfiq al-Rahman in the lessons of the Qur'an, (3/498), Faisal bin Abdul Aziz Al Mubarak.
- [26]. See: Tafsir Ibn Ashour (22/9).
- [27]. Songs, 3/245. By Abu Al-Faraj Al-Isfahani, and Diwan Al-Sabbabah (p.: 90) by Ibn Abi Hijla.
- [28]. See: Keys to the Unseen, 25/180 Al-Razi.
- [29]. See: Fath Al-Qadeer (4/269), Al-Shawkani.